

Using Sensing On-Board Passing Vehicles for the purpose of Virtual Sensing of Bridges

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Abstract

The dynamics of bridges and (traversing) vehicles are coupled through the contact forces at the interface between the two subsystems. This study proposes the concept of virtual sensing (response reconstruction) in bridges using information from on-board sensors installed on an instrumented vehicle with known dynamic characteristics. The premise of the proposed approach is that contact force estimation requires knowing solely the properties of the vehicle model and information from on-board sensors, and, subsequently, using the Augmented Kalman Filter (AKF) technique. Interestingly, the proposed contact force estimation scheme does not necessitate knowledge of the rail profile irregularities characteristics, even though the contact forces depend on them. The estimated contact forces become then input to a finite element model of the traversed bridge, which enables the reconstruction of bridge response (acceleration, displacement, strains, stresses, etc). The estimated strain/stress time histories on the bridge can provide valuable information on the health status of the bridge. The proposed approach is verified with the aid of simulated data from railway bridge-vehicle interaction analyses, examining a 10-degree-of-freedom vehicle model that is representative of realistic train vehicles. The railway bridge considered is a simply supported Euler-Bernoulli beam model. The results offer valuable insights into the effects of different factors (measurement and model errors, vehicle speed, and rail irregularities) on the accuracy of contact force estimation and bridge response reconstruction, and suggest an optimal sensor configuration based on the minimum number of sensors required and their location on the vehicle.

Keywords: On-board sensing; virtual sensing; bridges; fatigue; input-state estimation; response reconstruction

1. Introduction

Bridges are an essential part of transportation infrastructure. It is thus crucial to effectively assess their structural condition to guarantee robustness and reliability during operation. Traditionally, structural health monitoring (SHM) of bridges relies on sensors mounted at different locations on the target bridge [1]. Despite being well-established under different loading conditions [2–6], such techniques come with significant installation, labor, and maintenance expenses. As a

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result, only a very small fraction of existing bridges around the world is monitored [7, 8]. Without information about their health status, most bridges remain in operation without knowledge of impending failure.

10 In view of the vast number of bridges that need to be monitored, scalable solutions have become necessary. An alternative to traditional SHM techniques is to process measurements from instrumented traversing vehicles to extract information about the health status of bridges [9], which is known as vehicle scanning of bridges [10] or indirect bridge modal parameter identification [11–13]. This approach is based on the realization that the vehicle and bridge are coupled when the vehicle traverses the bridge; thus, vital information regarding the status of the bridge can be extracted by the instrumented vehicle’s response. Compared to traditional methods, vehicle scanning has the potential to provide a rapid and scalable diagnostic approach and a variety of information about the health status of bridges.

For instance, vehicle scanning methods have been proposed for extracting bridge modal features, 20 including modal frequencies [9, 14–22], mode shapes [15, 16, 23–27], and damping ratios [22, 26–28]. Yang et al. pioneered such approaches by processing different signals extracted from scanning vehicles, including vehicle acceleration [9], contact point response [14–16], and residual contact point response [17, 18]. Jin et al. [20, 21] proposed a method that utilizes stochastic subspace identification to estimate bridge frequencies from vehicle response. Malekjafarian and O’Brien adopted time-frequency domain decomposition [23] and Hilbert Huang transform [24] to estimate mode shapes from vehicle acceleration measurements. Eshkevari et al. [26, 27] investigated the use of mobile sensor networks and convex optimization techniques to identify modal information. More recently, Erduran et al. [19] applied a continuous wavelet transform (CWT) on the acceleration record of bogies to estimate bridge frequencies. Zhou et al. [25] tested a two-peak spectrum 30 idealized filter technique for extracting both modal frequencies and mode shapes.

Vehicle scanning has also been applied in conjunction with signal-processing techniques to identify the existence and location of damage on bridges. Nguyen and Tran [29] proposed a CWT to process the response of vehicles for damage detection. McGetrick and Kim [30] applied CWT with different wavelets on the acceleration of vehicle axles to detect damage on the bridge, both numerically and experimentally. Kildashti et al. [31] attempted to identify the location and level of cable damage in a cable-stayed bridge by solely analyzing vehicle response measurements. Lei et al. [32] suggested the use of discrete wavelet transform analysis on the residual contact response of a moving vehicle to detect bridge damage (cracks) when road roughness is present.

Vehicle scanning techniques have also been used to extract road [33–36] and rail [37, 38] rough- 40 ness profiles with the aid of Kalman filtering techniques [33–38] and neural network algorithms [39, 40]. For example, Zeng et al. [33] suggested a combination of an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) and a Discrete Kalman Filter to estimate the road roughness from tire pressure. Xiao et al. [38] attempted to calculate track irregularities and bridge natural frequencies from vehicle response measurements based on a recursive Bayesian Kalman filtering algorithm. Dertimanis et al. [37], Zhao et al. [34, 35], He and Yang [36], and Yang et al. [41] also proposed different variants of Kalman Filters (including the Dual Kalman Filter [37], Augmented Kalman Filter (AKF) [34, 35], Discrete Kalman filter [36], and EKF [41]) to estimate road roughness from vehicle response measurements.

The aim of the present study is to extend the scope of vehicle scanning to bridge response 50 reconstruction and, more specifically, strain/stress reconstruction. Assuming an available bridge model, monitoring stresses would allow for reflecting the structural health of a bridge, including fatigue evaluation. Key to stress estimation is the estimation of the unknown contact forces, which involves solving an input-state estimation problem [42–45]. Towards this direction, Chen et al. [46]

utilized an EKF to estimate the contact forces resulting from vehicle-bridge interaction using tire pressure measurements, while Wang et al. [47] applied an AKF to estimate the contact force using the road vehicle response. Both models [46, 47] assumed a viscoelastic contact for the vehicle, which is primarily applicable to road vehicles but not to trains. To this end, different to [46, 47], this study focuses on railway bridges, which are traversed by trains, and, thus, assumes a rigid contact process to approximate the physics of the wheel-rail contact forces. In lieu of field tests, we derive the on-board sensor measurements from dynamic simulations of nominal coupled vehicle-bridge systems. To estimate the contact forces, we employ an AKF. To account for measurement uncertainties we contaminate the dynamic simulations with noise, while to account also for modeling uncertainties we use a perturbed model to carry out the AKF estimations. By means of numerical case studies, we demonstrate the effectiveness and robustness of this approach in contact force estimation and bridge response reconstruction. Lastly, we investigate the least number and optimal location of strain and acceleration sensors that provide sufficiently accurate estimates of the contact forces.

2. Vehicle bridge interaction modeling

We consider a vehicle-bridge system in the vertical (pitch-bounce vehicle axis, longitudinal-vertical bridge axis) plane, where the bridge and the vehicle are both multi-degree of freedom (MDOF) systems. We model the bridge with Euler-Bernoulli beam elements and the vehicle as a multi-body assembly with m degrees of freedom (DOFs) in total (Figure 1). The contact forces $\lambda(t)$ between the vehicle and the bridge couple the vehicle-bridge system and constitute the means of vehicle-bridge interaction (VBI) [48–51].

Figure 1: 10-DOF train vehicle on a simply supported bridge

The governing equation of motion (EOM) of the vehicle subsystem, assuming that the vehicle moves at a constant speed (i.e., the vehicle is in a state of static equilibrium along its longitudinal axis), is [48–51]:

$$\mathbf{M}_v \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_v(t) + \mathbf{C}_v \dot{\mathbf{u}}_v(t) + \mathbf{K}_v \mathbf{u}_v(t) - \mathbf{W}_v \lambda(t) = \mathbf{f}_v \quad (1)$$

where the subscript $(\cdot)_v$ denotes the vehicle subsystem, and \mathbf{M}_v , \mathbf{C}_v , and \mathbf{K}_v are, respectively, the mass, damping, and stiffness matrices of the vehicle. $\mathbf{u}_v(t)$ is the displacement vector of the vehicle

system, and \mathbf{f}_v is a force vector containing the external loads acting on the vehicle. Note that the following analysis ignores the self-weight of the vehicle. In other words, the equilibrium conditions are stated with respect to the deformed (static) configuration under the self-weight of the vehicle. Lastly, $\boldsymbol{\lambda}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\lambda \times 1}$ is a contact force vector, and $\mathbf{W}_v \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n_\lambda}$ is a contact direction matrix, mapping the contact forces to the DOFs of the wheels, where n_λ is the number of contact points [50, 51].

Similarly, the EOM of the bridge at the deformed (static) configuration under its self-weight is:

$$\mathbf{M}_b \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_b(t) + \mathbf{C}_b \dot{\mathbf{u}}_b(t) + \mathbf{K}_b \mathbf{u}_b(t) + \mathbf{W}_b \boldsymbol{\lambda}(t) = \mathbf{f}_b \quad (2)$$

where the subscript $(\)_b$ denotes the bridge subsystem. \mathbf{M}_b , \mathbf{C}_b , and \mathbf{K}_b are, respectively, the mass, damping, and stiffness matrices of the bridge, and $\mathbf{u}_b(t)$ is the displacement vector of the bridge. \mathbf{f}_b is the force vector containing external loads acting on the bridge. As a first approach, the only external loading considered in this study is the static weight of the vehicle. Other external loads, such as earthquake or wind loads and aerodynamic forces, could be incorporated in the formulation, e.g., through the \mathbf{f}_b force vector as in [52]. $\mathbf{W}_b \in \mathbb{R}^{n_b \times n_\lambda}$ is a contact direction matrix mapping the contact force to the bridge's DOF [50, 51], where n_b is the number of DOFs of the bridge.

If the contact force vector $\boldsymbol{\lambda}(t)$ is known (as in the following sections), we can solve Eqs. (1) and (2) independently. However, if $\boldsymbol{\lambda}(t)$ is an unknown, we need to solve Eqs. (1) and (2) as a coupled system. The EOM of the coupled system is:

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{C} \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{W} \boldsymbol{\lambda}(t) = \mathbf{f} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{u} = [\mathbf{u}_v^T \ \mathbf{u}_b^T]^T$ is the displacement vector of the whole system, and \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C} , and \mathbf{K} are, respectively, the mass, damping, and stiffness matrices of the whole system:

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_v & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{M}_b \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_v & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{C}_b \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_v & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}_b \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

$\mathbf{W} = [-\mathbf{W}_v^T \ \mathbf{W}_b^T]^T$ is the contact direction matrix of the coupled system, and $\mathbf{f} = [\mathbf{f}_v^T \ \mathbf{f}_b^T]^T$ is the joint force vector of the coupled system. Note that the superscript $(\)^T$ denotes the transpose of a vector or matrix.

Next step in solving the coupled vehicle-bridge system is the modeling of the contact mechanism between the wheels and the rails. This study assumes a rigid contact model, i.e., the vehicle's wheels are in continuous contact with the rails/bridge without overlapping or compliance between the rail and the wheel. Mathematically, this translates to a zero relative displacement $\mathbf{g}_N(x, t) = \mathbf{0}$, velocity $\dot{\mathbf{g}}_N(x, t) = \mathbf{0}$ and acceleration $\ddot{\mathbf{g}}_N(x, t) = \mathbf{0}$, between the two subsystems at the contact point [49, 51].

$$\mathbf{g}_N(x, t) = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{r}_c = \mathbf{0} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{r}_c is an irregularity vector storing the irregularities at each contact point. Herein, we model the rail irregularities (Figure 2) as stationary stochastic processes using the spectral representation method [48]. The irregularities parameters are defined according to the German spectra for high-speed railway [53].

Based on the assumption of rigid contact, the explicit expression for the contact force is:

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda} = -\mathbf{G}_w^{-1} [\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{M}^{-1} (\mathbf{f} - \mathbf{C} \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) - \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u}(t)) + 2v \mathbf{W}'^T \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + v^2 \mathbf{W}''^T \mathbf{u}(t) - v^2 \mathbf{r}_c''] \quad (6)$$

Figure 2: Sample profiles of (a) “very good” quality (b) “good” quality irregularities according to the German spectra for high-speed railway [53].

where \mathbf{G}_w^{-1} is the contact (coupling) mass between the bridge and the vehicle’s wheels, the inverse of which is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{G}_w = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{W} \quad (7)$$

Eq. 6 shows that the contact force depends on the characteristics and response of both vehicle and bridge subsystems. Besides, the rail irregularities profile highly affects the contact force. In this study, we employ the Newmark- β method to solve the coupled system of equations (3) and (6) [48–51].

3. Equation of motion of the train in modal coordinates

In this study, we focus on contact force estimation based on measurements extracted by a vehicle traversing a target bridge. To this end, later in Section 4.2 we deploy an AKF assuming known vehicle properties. For the needs of the AKF formulation we adopt the mode superposition method to describe the dynamics of the vehicle. In this context, we need to separate any rigid body (zero frequency) modes manifested in the vehicle model, from the flexible (deformation) modes. Therefore, we establish a relationship between the physical and modal coordinates of the (train) vehicle, by introducing a partitioned mass-normalized mode shape matrix as:

$$\mathbf{\Phi} = [\mathbf{\Phi}_{rigid} \quad \mathbf{\Phi}_{flex}] \quad (8)$$

Matrix $\mathbf{\Phi}$ comprises all m_0 zero-frequency rigid body mode shape(s) $\mathbf{\Phi}_{rigid}$ and all m_f flexible mode shape(s) $\mathbf{\Phi}_{flex}$ (where $m_f = m - m_0$). Thus, we can express the displacement vector of the vehicle by using matrix $\mathbf{\Phi}$ as:

$$\mathbf{u}_v(t) = \mathbf{\Phi} \boldsymbol{\xi}(t) \quad (9)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\xi}(t)$ represents the modal displacement vector. It is important to note that our analysis bypasses the need to measure static deformation in the vehicle (which is impractical using on-board

sensors). We can partition accordingly the modal displacement vector into two parts

$$\boldsymbol{\xi} = [\boldsymbol{\xi}_{rigid}^T \quad \boldsymbol{\xi}_{flex}^T]^T \quad (10)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\xi}_{rigid}$ is the modal displacement of the rigid body mode(s) and $\boldsymbol{\xi}_{flex}$ is the modal displacement of the flexible modes. By substituting Eq. (9) into Eq. (1) and pre-multiplying both sides by $\boldsymbol{\Phi}^T$, we can obtain the EOM of the vehicle in modal coordinates:

$$\ddot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{rigid} = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{rigid}^T \mathbf{W}_v \boldsymbol{\lambda}(t) \quad (11)$$

$$\ddot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{flex} + \mathbf{Z}_{flex} \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{flex} + \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{flex} \boldsymbol{\xi}_{flex} = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex}^T \mathbf{W}_v \boldsymbol{\lambda}(t) \quad (12)$$

with $\mathbf{Z}_{flex} = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex}^T \mathbf{C}_v \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{flex} = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex}^T \mathbf{K}_v \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex}$. Eq. (12) may be coupled since the system may not be classically damped (i.e., the modal damping matrix \mathbf{Z}_{flex} may not be diagonalizable). This is due to the fact that localized damping elements, related to primary and secondary suspension, are introduced between different degrees of freedom. For the case where the modes are classically damped, the matrix \mathbf{Z}_{flex} is diagonal with the r -th diagonal element given by $Z_{rr} = 2\zeta_r \omega_r$, where ζ_r , $r = m_0 + 1, \dots, m$ are the modal damping ratios for the flexible modes of the vehicle. From Eq. (8)-(12), we derive the displacement of all DOFs in modal coordinates as:

$$\mathbf{u}_v(t) = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{rigid} \boldsymbol{\xi}_{rigid}(t) + \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex} \boldsymbol{\xi}_{flex}(t) \quad (13)$$

the acceleration of all DOF as:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_v(t) &= \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{rigid} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{rigid}^T \mathbf{W}_v \boldsymbol{\lambda}(t) + \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex} \ddot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{flex}(t) \\ &= [\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{rigid} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{rigid}^T + \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex}^T] \mathbf{W}_v \boldsymbol{\lambda}(t) - \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex} \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{flex} \boldsymbol{\xi}_{flex} - \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex} \mathbf{Z}_{flex} \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{flex} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

and the strain at the suspension springs as:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(t) &= \boldsymbol{\Psi} \mathbf{u}_v(t) \\ &= \boldsymbol{\Psi} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{rigid} \boldsymbol{\xi}_{rigid}(t) + \boldsymbol{\Psi} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex} \boldsymbol{\xi}_{flex}(t) \\ &= \boldsymbol{\Psi} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex} \boldsymbol{\xi}_{flex}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Psi}$ is the matrix that associates the displacements at all DOFs to the strains at the springs of the train vehicle model. The term $\boldsymbol{\Psi} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{rigid} \boldsymbol{\xi}_{rigid}(t)$ in Eq. (15) disappears because the rigid body modes do not contribute to strains in the vehicle. The equations developed (Eq. (13)-(15)) are in a form that the AKF can directly use for estimating the unknown contact forces.

4. Contact force estimation using vehicle measurements

4.1. State-space model of the vehicle in modal coordinates

We can represent the modal equations of motion for the train vehicle model in state-space form by introducing the state vector $\mathbf{x}(t) = [\boldsymbol{\xi}_{flex}^T \quad \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{flex}^T]^T$:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}_c \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}_c \boldsymbol{\lambda}(t) \quad (16)$$

where the state matrix \mathbf{A}_c and the input matrix \mathbf{B}_c are:

$$\mathbf{A}_c = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \\ -\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{flex} & -\mathbf{Z}_{flex} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B}_c = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex}^T \mathbf{W}_v \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

At time instant $t_k = k\Delta t$, where k is the time step index and Δt is the sampling time interval, we denote the value of the state-space vector as \mathbf{x}_k and the contact force as $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_k$, (i.e., $\mathbf{x}_k \equiv \mathbf{x}(k\Delta t)$ and $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_k \equiv \boldsymbol{\lambda}(k\Delta t)$). We can express the discrete state-space form of the EOM for the train vehicle under the zero-order hold assumption as:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{A}_d \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{B}_d \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k + \mathbf{w}_k \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_d = e^{\mathbf{A}_c \Delta t}$ and $\mathbf{B}_d = (\mathbf{A}_d - \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{A}_c^{-1} \mathbf{B}_c$ for non-singular \mathbf{A}_c . The process noise \mathbf{w}_k is assumed to be zero-mean Gaussian, i.e. $\mathbf{w}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q}_x)$ with process noise covariance $\mathbf{Q}_x \in \mathbb{R}^{2m_f \times 2m_f}$.

Let \mathbf{y}_k represent the vector of N_0 measured quantities, which includes accelerations and strains at the vehicle in physical coordinates. We can express the observation equation as:

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{G} \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{J} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k + \mathbf{v}_k \quad (19)$$

where the measurement error term follows a zero-mean Gaussian distribution, i.e. $\mathbf{v}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q}_y)$, with measurement error covariance $\mathbf{Q}_y \in \mathbb{R}^{N_0 \times N_0}$, and

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} -\mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex}\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{flex} & -\mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex}\mathbf{Z}_{flex} \\ \mathbf{S}\boldsymbol{\Psi}\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{flex} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{J} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\Phi}\boldsymbol{\Phi}^T \mathbf{W}_v \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

110 which are readily derived from Eqs. (14) and (15) for all acceleration and strain measurements, respectively. \mathbf{H} and \mathbf{S} are the selection matrices that map the acceleration and strain vectors to the selected acceleration and strain measurements at sensor locations.

4.2. Review of AKF for unknown contact force estimation

To estimate the unknown contact force vector $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_k \equiv \boldsymbol{\lambda}(k\Delta t)$ applied on the wheels of the vehicle from the bridge/rail using AKF [42] [cite AKF paper here], we need to model the changes in contact force at each time step. To this end, we introduce the following random walk model to describe the contact force vector at each time step:

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}_{k+1} = \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k + \boldsymbol{\eta}_k \quad (21)$$

where the change in force $\boldsymbol{\eta}_k$ follows a zero-mean Gaussian distribution, i.e. $\boldsymbol{\eta}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q}_\lambda)$ with covariance matrix $\mathbf{Q}_\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\lambda \times n_\lambda}$. To incorporate the contact force vector as part of the system's state variables, we introduce the augmented state vector $\mathbf{x}_k^a = [\mathbf{x}_k^T \quad \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k^T]^T$. The augmented state-space model and observation equation take the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{k+1}^a &= \mathbf{A}^a \mathbf{x}_k^a + \boldsymbol{\zeta}_k \\ \mathbf{y}_k &= \mathbf{G}^a \mathbf{x}_k^a + \mathbf{v}_k \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where the augmented state-transition matrix $\mathbf{A}^a \in \mathbb{R}^{(2m_f+n_\lambda) \times (2m_f+n_\lambda)}$ and the augmented observation matrix $\mathbf{G}^a \in \mathbb{R}^{N_0 \times (2m_f+n_\lambda)}$ are:

$$\mathbf{A}^a = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_d & \mathbf{B}_d \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{G}^a = [\mathbf{G} \quad \mathbf{J}] \quad (23)$$

while the augmented process noise covariance matrix $\mathbf{Q}_a \in \mathbb{R}^{(2m_f+n_\lambda) \times (2m_f+n_\lambda)}$ of the zero-mean Gaussian white noise sequence $\boldsymbol{\zeta}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q}_a)$ is:

$$\mathbf{Q}_a = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_x & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{Q}_\lambda \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

We employ the Kalman filter to estimate the augmented state vector, which provides the augmented state estimation $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k}^a$ and the error covariance matrix $\mathbf{P}_{k|k} \in \mathbb{R}^{(2m_f+n_\lambda) \times (2m_f+n_\lambda)}$. We achieve this by performing the following time update step:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}^a &= \mathbf{A}^a \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1|k-1}^a \\ \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} &= \mathbf{A}^a \mathbf{P}_{k-1|k-1} (\mathbf{A}^a)^T + \mathbf{Q}_a\end{aligned}\tag{25}$$

and measurement update step:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{K}_k &= \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} (\mathbf{G}^a)^T (\mathbf{G}^a \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} (\mathbf{G}^a)^T + \mathbf{Q}_y)^{-1} \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k}^a &= \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}^a + \mathbf{K}_k (\mathbf{y}_k - \mathbf{G}^a \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}^a) \\ \mathbf{P}_{k|k} &= \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} - \mathbf{K}_k \mathbf{G}^a \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}\end{aligned}\tag{26}$$

By estimating the augmented state vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k}^a$, we infer the contact forces which constitute a partition of the augmented state vector. Then, we can derive displacements, accelerations, and strains at desired locations in the vehicle with the help of Eqs. (13), (14), and (15). Also, using Eq. (2) with the estimated contact forces, we can fully reconstruct the response quantities of the bridge, including displacements, accelerations, strains, and stresses.

5. Verification using Vehicle-Bridge Interaction Simulations

120 To evaluate the performance of the proposed AKF approach, we employ simulated data from coupled (railway) bridge - (train) vehicle systems. The goal is to thoroughly investigate the impact of various factors on the reliability of contact force reconstruction and showcase the potential of virtual sensing for bridge monitoring. Those factors include measurement error, model error related to the dynamics of the train vehicle, irregularities in the rail profile, vehicle speed, and different sensor configurations.

To account for measurement errors in AKF, we use simulated, noise-contaminated, measurements. To account for measurement and model errors, in addition to noise-contaminated measurements, we use a slightly different vehicle model in AKF to estimate the contact forces, derived by perturbing the properties of the model, such as mass properties, stiffness, and damping coefficient
130 of the suspensions. Specifically, we get a noise-contaminated measurement y_k at time instant k by $y_k = a_k + \epsilon_{me} I_a \tilde{w}_k$, where \tilde{w}_k , $k = 1, \dots, N$, is a zero-mean unit-variance white noise sequence, a_k is the simulated response time history from a nominal vehicle-bridge interaction model and I_a is the intensity of the simulated response a_k obtained as the root mean square of the response. To obtain a perturbed vehicle model, we modify the values of nominal properties X_{nom} of the model to X_{pert} as follows: $X_{pert} = X_{nom}(1 + \epsilon_{mo} \tilde{w})$, where \tilde{w} is a sample from a zero-mean unit-variance Gaussian variable. Note that X can be any property of the vehicle such as mass, stiffness, and damping. The values of ϵ_{me} and ϵ_{mo} denote the level of measurement and model error considered, respectively. Either nominal or perturbed vehicle models are used with AKF to carry out contact force estimations and predict output quantities of interest.

140 In the following examples, the vehicle enters the bridge at $t = 1$ s and moves along a 30 m long simply supported bridge modeled with Euler-Bernoulli beams. The bridge is 30 m long with mass per unit length 41.74 t/m, modulus of elasticity $E = 28.25$ GPa, Poisson ratio 0.2, damping ratio $\zeta = 2\%$ cross-sectional area 7.73 m², and moment of inertia 7.84 m⁴ [48].

5.1. 10-DOF vehicle on a smooth track

This section examines a 10-DOF Pioneer train vehicle (Figure 1) moving at $v = 100\text{km/h}$ on a smooth track. The vehicle model adopted is representative of the main dynamics of a real train vehicle and allows us to test the reliability of AKF in predicting multiple unknown contact forces. Table 1 lists the nominal and perturbed mechanical properties of the train [54]. The perturbed values correspond to $\varepsilon_{mo} = 5\%$.

Table 1: Nominal and perturbed values of the mechanical properties of the 10-DOF Pioneer train model.

Property	Nominal value	Perturbed value	Property	Nominal value	Perturbed value
m_c (t)	42.4	41.67	$k_{x,p}$ (MN/m)	9	8.71
I_c (tm ²)	1064.4	1064.4	c_s (kNs/m)	33	32.68
m_t (kg)	3.4	3.56	$c_{x,s}$ (kNs/m)	0	0
I_t (tm ²)	7.2	7.2	c_p (kNs/m)	30	26.19
m_w (t)	2.2	2.21	$c_{x,p}$ (kNs/m)	0	0
k_s (MN/m)	0.4	0.38	l_t (m)	9	9
$k_{x,s}$ (MN/m)	0.24	0.23	l_w (m)	1.25	1.25
k_p (MNm)	1.04	1.10			

150 The state error covariance, \mathbf{Q}_x , equals to $10^{-8}\mathbf{I}$, where \mathbf{I} is an identity matrix. \mathbf{Q}_y , the covariance matrix for the measurement error, has diagonal elements that are 10^{-4} times the mean square value of the measured response time history. This value corresponds to 1% of the root mean square of the measured response time history. We establish the value of the covariance matrix \mathbf{Q}_λ for the random walk model by an L-curve analysis [42].

Figure 3 compares the “actual” and estimated contact force of all wheels using acceleration measurements at all vertical DOFs of the vehicle and strain measurements of all suspensions under different errors. Figure 4 shows the corresponding estimation error of contact forces. Within the context of this study, the term “actual” refers to the response acquired from the coupled vehicle-bridge simulation. Also, we define the estimation error as $\varepsilon_{est} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (p_{i,k} - p_{i,est,k})^2 / \max|p_{i,k}|}$, where
160 $p_{i,k}$ and $p_{i,est,k}$ are the “actual” and estimated contact force of the i^{th} wheel at the k^{th} time step, respectively, and N is the number of time steps considered.

Figure 3 shows that the AKF can reconstruct all wheels’ contact force histories using the accelerations and strain measurements without noise. The reconstructed contact forces are identical to the “actual” contact forces. Note that the proposed method can also capture the sudden change in contact force that occurs due to the rapid change in the wheels’ response when entering or exiting the bridge. Even with the presence of errors (5% measurement error only, and 5% measurement error and 5% model error), there are only minor differences between the estimation and the ground truth, which are practically negligible. This demonstrates the effectiveness and robustness of AKF in unknown contact force estimation with the presence of model and measurement uncertainty.

170 To examine the effect of speed on the performance of the AKF in estimating the unknown contact force, we also study the same vehicle-bridge system at a higher vehicle speed $v = 250\text{km/h}$. That is to say, a speed that is more akin to the present operational velocity of modern trains. Figure 5 shows the “actual” and estimated contact forces of wheel 1 (Figure 5 (a)), wheel 2 (Figure 5 (b)), wheel 3 (Figure 5 (c)), and wheel 4 (Figure 5 (d)) using the same measurement configuration under different uncertainty conditions, while Figure 6 shows the corresponding estimation errors of the contact forces. When there is no error in the measurements and train model, the estimated contact forces are in excellent agreement and almost identical to the actual contact forces. Even

Figure 3: Comparison between the “actual” and estimated contact force of (a) wheel 1, (b) wheel 2, (c) wheel 3, and (d) wheel 4 using acceleration measurement at all translation DOF and strain measurement of all suspensions with different levels of error considered ($v = 100\text{km/h}$) (no irregularity).

Figure 4: Estimation error of all contact forces using acceleration measurement at all translation DOF and strain measurement of all suspensions with different levels of error considered ($v = 100\text{km/h}$) (no irregularity).

when errors are considered, the estimated contact forces closely match the “actual” contact forces imposed on the vehicle. This implies that the performance of the AKF in estimating contact force appears unaffected by the vehicle speed, at least for the two different speed levels considered in the examples studied.

Figure 5: Comparison between the “actual” and estimated contact force of (a) wheel 1, (b) wheel 2, (c) wheel 3, and (d) wheel 4 using acceleration measurements at all translation DOFs and strain measurements of all suspensions with different levels of error considered ($v = 250\text{km/h}$) (no irregularity).

Figure 6: Estimation error of all contact forces using acceleration measurement at all translation DOFs and strain measurements of all suspensions with different levels of error considered ($v = 250\text{km/h}$) (no irregularity).

5.2. 10-DOF vehicle on a rail with irregularity

In this section, we focus on the performance of AKF in estimating contact forces under a more complex excitation (i.e., in the presence of rail irregularities). To this end, we study a 10-DOF Pioneer train moving on the bridge with constant speed $v = 250\text{km/h}$, and assume “good quality”

rail irregularity conditions on both ground and bridge [53]. The rail irregularity is a specific realization of the stochastic process [48] obeying the rail irregularity spectra [53]. In line with the previous section, there is no change in the covariance of the state error \mathbf{Q}_x , the covariance of the measurement error \mathbf{Q}_y , and the selection criteria of the covariance for the random walk model \mathbf{Q}_λ .

190 For simplicity, Figure 7 depicts the contact force histories and spectra of wheel 1 (Figure 7(a), (b), and (e)), and of wheel 4 (Figure 7(c), (d), and (f)), while Figure 8 shows the errors of the estimated contact forces of all wheels under different levels of measurement and model error. When there is no measurement or modeling error, the AKF method accurately captures all high-frequency information of the contact force due to the excitation from rail irregularity. This results in the estimated contact forces being almost identical to the “actual” contact forces. Despite the presence of model uncertainty and measurement uncertainty, the AKF method can capture all intricate details of the contact force history. The excellent performance in estimating contact forces in the time domain shows the AKF method remains reliable and effective. It is evident that the AKF method can estimate the contact force of wheels 1 and 4 with good accuracy in frequency
200 domains as well, regardless of the uncertainty. This demonstrates the feasibility of applying AKF in real-life applications for estimating the contact forces of trains.

5.3. Effect of number and location of sensors

This section investigates an optimal sensor configuration (optimal in terms of the minimum number of sensors required and their location) to obtain reliable estimations. This allows us to place sensors effectively and wisely while achieving reasonable precision in contact force estimation. For this purpose, we reconstruct the contact forces acting on the wheels using different acceleration and strain measurement combinations. We consider a 5% measurement error and 5% model error in the following analysis. The train-bridge system studied remains the same as in Section 5.2.

Table 2: Estimation error of all contact forces using different combinations of acceleration and strain measurements ($v = 250\text{km/h}$) (“good quality” rail irregularity).

case	measurement combination	wheel 1	wheel 2	wheel 3	wheel 4
1	acceleration of all vertical DOFs + strain of all suspension	1.87%	1.95%	1.73%	1.79%
2	acceleration of car body and bogies + strain of all suspension	32.79%	32.48%	31.12%	31.56%
3	acceleration of all wheels + strain of all suspension	1.93%	1.94%	1.78%	1.80%
4	acceleration of all wheels only	26.27%	26.12%	13.64%	14.21%
5	acceleration of all wheels + strain of all secondary suspension	35.73%	35.70%	9.15%	9.49%
6	acceleration of all wheels + strain of all primary suspension	1.92%	1.93%	1.77%	1.79%
7	acceleration of all wheels + strain of primary suspension 2,3	2.58%	1.94%	1.78%	2.20%

First, we study the influence of removing the acceleration measurement at different DOFs.
210 Figure 9 compares the contact force histories and Fourier spectra of wheel 1 (Figure 9(a), (b), and (e)), and wheel 4 (Figure 9(c), (d), and (f)), while Table 2 shows the corresponding estimation errors of the contact forces of all wheels. Figure 9 (a)-(d) shows that by removing the wheel acceleration measurements (case 2), AKF fails to restructure the contact forces with the precision shown in the Section 5.2 (Figure 8). The spectra of contact forces of wheels 1 and 4 (Figure 9 (e) and (f)) show that errors appear in high-frequencies rather than low-frequencies. In contrast, removing acceleration measurement from the car body and bogies (case 3) only slightly affects contact force estimation. This indicates that wheel acceleration measurements, corresponding to acceleration measurements that are collocated with the unknown contact forces, are necessary for the AKF method to provide a reliable estimation of contact forces, while the acceleration
220 measurements at the car body and bogies are less important in accurate contact force estimation.

Figure 7: Comparison between the “actual” and estimated contact forces using acceleration measurements at all translation DOFs and strain measurements of all suspensions with different levels of error considered : (a) contact force history of wheel 1, (b) zoom-in of (a); (c) contact force history of wheel 4, (d) zoom-in of (c); Fourier spectrum of (e) wheel 1 and (f) wheel 4 ($v = 250\text{km/h}$) (“good quality” rail irregularity).

Similarly, we investigate the influence of removing strain measurements on the accuracy of contact force estimation. Figure 10 compares the contact force histories and spectra of wheels 1 (Figure 10(a), (b), and (e)) and 4 (Figure 10(c), (d), and (f)), and Table 2 shows the corresponding

Figure 8: Estimation error of all contact forces using acceleration measurement at all translation DOFs and strain measurements of all suspensions with different levels of error considered ($v = 250\text{km/h}$) (“good quality” irregularity).

estimation errors of the contact forces of all wheels. Figure 10 shows a low-frequency drift in the estimated contact force of wheel 1 and wheel 4 when we remove all strain measurements (case 4) or when we only have strain measurements from the secondary suspension system (case 5). When strain measurements at the primary suspension system are available (cases 6 and 7), the AKF method can provide a reliable estimation of the contact forces of wheels 1 and 4. One interesting finding is that we don’t need strain measurement of all primary suspensions to achieve a good estimation of the contact forces. As long as we have one primary suspension strain measurement on each bogie (i.e., the strain of the front or rear primary suspension of the bogies (case 7), the AKF method still gives a reasonably accurate estimation.

5.4. Bridge Response Reconstruction

This section focuses on bridge response reconstruction using the estimated contact forces from the AKF method with the minimum number of acceleration and strain sensors (case 7 in Section 5.3). We consider the same train-bridge system as in Section 5.2 and uncertainty (5% measurement error only, and a combination of 5% measurement error and 5% model error).

Figure 11 illustrates a comparison between the “actual” response of the bridge (obtained from the vehicle-bridge system simulation) and the reconstructed bridge response using the estimated contact forces. The reconstructed response is solely based on the solutions of the EOM of the bridge (Eq. 2) using the estimated contact forces from AKF, which utilizes acceleration measurement of all wheels and strain measurements at the second and third primary suspension. This assumes that we already know the bridge model and do not need to solve the coupled system EOM of the entire system, nor know the rail irregularities. The results comparison reveals excellent agreement in the time history of displacement (Figure 11(a)), acceleration (Figure 11(c) and (d)) and (top surface) normal stress (Figure 11(e) and (f)) at the midspan of the bridge. The estimated envelope deflection of the entire bridge (Figure 11(b)) has a great fit with the “actual” envelope when there is a 5 % measurement error. Even when there is also a 5 % modeling error, the reconstructed responses are reasonably accurate. This suggests that the proposed vehicle scanning approach with AKF estimation of the contact force holds promise for reconstructing the bridge’s response (virtual sensing) without any knowledge about the rail irregularities and could be useful for SHM applications. In particular, using S-N fatigue curves and linear fatigue damage accumulation law [55, 56] the reliable estimates of stress time histories can be used for providing reliable estimates of the fatigue damage accumulation throughout the metallic components of the bridge due to trains traversing the bridge.

Figure 9: Comparison of the “actual” and estimated contact forces using different acceleration measurement combinations: (a) contact force history of wheel 1, (b) zoom-in of (a); (c) contact force history of wheel 4, (d) zoom-in of (c); Fourier spectrum of (e) wheel 1 and (f) wheel 4 ($v = 250\text{km/h}$) (“good quality” rail irregularity).

6. Conclusions

This paper proposes the application of an AKF approach for identifying the unknown vehicle-bridge contact forces for use in bridge virtual sensing based solely on on-board sensor measurements (on an instrumented vehicle). To implement the AKF on the vehicle subsystem, we adopt mode

Figure 10: Comparison of the “actual” and estimated contact forces using different strain measurement combinations: (a) contact force history of wheel 1, (b) zoom-in of (a); (c) contact force history of wheel 4, (d) zoom-in of (c); Fourier spectrum of (e) wheel 1 and (f) wheel 4 ($v = 250\text{km/h}$) (“good quality” rail irregularity).

260 superposition to separate the rigid from the flexible modes and formulate a state-space model of the vehicle using solely the flexible modes. As field measurements are not available, we generate artificial measurements from a numerical simulation on a coupled vehicle-bridge system. Specifically, the vehicle-bridge simulations investigate a 10-DOF pioneer train model at varying speeds

Figure 11: Comparison between the “actual” and reconstructed bridge response: (a) displacement response history, (b) envelope of the deflection of the bridge, (c) acceleration response history, (d) zoom in of (c), (e) normal stress history of the top surface at the midspan of the bridge, and (f) zoom in of (e) ($v = 250\text{km/h}$) (“good quality” rail irregularity).

and rail irregularities. To account for measurement and modeling errors, the analysis adopts noise-contaminated measurements and a perturbed vehicle model with AKF. The high accuracy in contact force estimation with properly tuned force model covariance suggests that the AKF is robust and reliable in the presence of model uncertainty and measurement error. Additionally, the study examines an optimal sensor configuration for contact force estimation.

270 The results show that acceleration measurements at all wheels and strain measurements of at least one primary suspension per bogies are critical for accurate force estimation. Furthermore, the analysis demonstrates the precision of reconstructing bridge response through estimated contact force, provided the prior knowledge of the bridge model. Importantly no knowledge of rail irregularities is needed to estimate the contact forces or reconstruct the dynamics of the bridge from vibration measurements on-board the vehicle. In general, these initial findings highlight the

capability of virtual sensing using on-board sensors and strengthen the potential of the vehicle scanning method for bridge monitoring purposes.

To enhance the performance of the proposed method, future work should focus on exploring the accuracy of different Bayesian filtering techniques for input-state estimation. This will help identify the most effective approach for filtering the sensor data for the purpose of virtual sensing.

280 Additionally, future work could consider nonlinearities in the vehicle's suspension system and a 3D model of the vehicle-bridge system to obtain a more accurate representation of the behavior of realistic vehicle-bridge systems.

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